

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Intonation analysis of Carnatic violin performances in Thodi and Kalyani

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Supervisor: Martín Rocamora

Co-Supervisor: Thomas Nuttall

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Abstract

This thesis explores the intonation characteristics of Carnatic violin performances, focusing on the ragas Thodi and Kalyani. The study aims to address the gap in research on violin intonation in Carnatic music, which has previously primarily concentrated on vocal intonation and sustained pitch notes. Utilizing existing pitch tracking algorithms and statistical analysis, this research investigates Carnatic violin intonation within these specific ragas, focusing on 1) its alignment with the 22-*Sruti* tuning system, 2) specific intonation characteristics of individual swaras, and 3) statistical comparisons with vocal intonation.

The methodology involves selecting tracks from the Saraga Carnatic dataset, extracting predominant pitch contours using the Melodia algorithm, and processing these contours to compute pitch histograms and kernel density estimates (KDEs). Peak parameters have been derived from these distributions to investigate specific swara-based intonation against known musicological insights. Statistical tests, including t-tests, U-tests and cross-entropy measurements, have been performed to compare pitch distributions across different sections of the performances and between vocal and violin tracks.

The findings highlight both swara-wise and overall intonation differences between violin and vocal performances. The violin shows sharper, more focused peaks in the pitch distributions, whereas the vocals exhibit broader, noisier peaks. Swara-wise results reveal that the intonation generally aligns with musicological expectations for both rāgas, however there is a discrepancy in the rendering of Suddha Dhaivatham (D1) in Thodi and Kaakali Nishadham (N3) in Kalyani between the violin and vocals. In raga-wise statistical comparisons, Thodi demonstrates greater variability in violin intonation, while Kalyani shows more consistency, likely due to Thodi's expressive playing style with wider oscillations. Section-wise statistical tests reveal that the intonation remains relatively consistent between the violin's main and alaa-pana sections but diverges in the solo section, suggesting that vocal accompaniment in the main and alaa-pana sections influences the violin, while the solo sections allow

for a more independent performance style.

These results contribute to a deeper understanding of the expressive nuances in Carnatic violin performances and suggest potential directions for future research in both musicology and computational music analysis.

Keywords: Carnatic violin, Intonation analysis, pitch tracking, Thodi, Kalyani

Chapter 1

Introduction

Carnatic music, one of the two major traditions of Indian art music, originated in the temples and royal courts of South India, which is characterized by a deeply structured system that emphasizes both compositional and improvisational elements [1]. The framework of Carnatic music is built upon *rāgas* (melodic frameworks) and *tālas* (rhythmic cycles), with *rāgas* serving as the foundation for melody creation. Each *rāga* is characterized by a specific set of notes, known as *swaras*, and distinct patterns of ornamentation called *gamakas*, which give each *rāga* its unique identity. These *gamakas* are integral to the expressive nature of the music, as they involve pitch oscillations and microtonal variations that are essential to the performance [2].

Intonation in Carnatic music refers to both the tuning of the notes and the way the pitch of a *swara* is interpreted in a performance. Unlike Western music, where tuning is typically fixed to a standardized scale (such as equal temperament), the intonation in Carnatic music is fluid and context-dependent. The pitch of a given *swara* can vary depending on the *rāga* being performed, the artist's stylistic interpretation, and even the specific section of the composition [3].

In recent years, computational approaches have been increasingly applied to analyze the intonation of *rāgas* in Carnatic music. These studies have employed techniques such as pitch tracking and statistical modeling to create detailed profiles of how each *swara* is intonated across different performances. For example, research by

Koduri et al. has explored the use of performance pitch histograms and context-based svara distributions to automatically extract intonation characteristics from audio recordings [3].

Understanding the intonation patterns in Carnatic music is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, it contributes to the broader field of musicology by providing empirical data on the microtonal structures that define Indian classical music. Secondly, it has practical applications in the development of music information retrieval (MIR) systems, which can be used for tasks such as rāga recognition, artist identification, and the generation of educational tools for music students.

This thesis builds on previous work by examining the intonation of specific rāgas in Carnatic violin performances, with a focus on the rāgas Thodi and Kalyani. By applying a combination of pitch tracking algorithms and statistical analysis, this study aims to shed light on the nuanced ways in which intonation varies not only between different performances but also between vocal and instrumental renditions of the same rāga. The findings of this research will contribute to a deeper understanding of the expressive capabilities of the Carnatic violin and provide insights that are relevant to both performers and scholars of Indian classical music.

1.1 Motivation

The study of intonation in Carnatic violin performances holds significant importance in both musicology and computational music analysis, as it plays a critical role in delivering a rāga's emotional expression and musical identity. Although substantial research has been conducted on Carnatic intonation, the focus has predominantly been on vocal intonation, particularly sustained pitch notes. The violin, as the primary melodic accompaniment, intricately mirrors the vocal style through ornamentation and microtonal variations. Despite its relevance, research on how violinists achieve intonation, particularly in specific rāgas like Thodi and Kalyani, remains limited.

This research aims to address the gap by focusing on the violin's role in delivering a

rāga's emotional expression and musical identity. By analyzing pitch distributions and incorporating more than just sustained notes and mean swara positions, this study seeks to offer a more comprehensive understanding of intonation in Carnatic violin performances.

1.2 Objectives

- To develop and utilize computational methods for pitch tracking and pitch histogram analysis.
- Examine whether violin intonation aligns more closely with Equal Temperament or the 22-*sruti* Just Intonation system.
- Conduct in-depth swara intonation analysis and compare against known musicological insights.
- Carry out a comprehensive statistical analysis by comparing pitch distributions between violin and vocal sections and obtain quantitative results for the same.

1.3 Structure of the Report

This report is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1: Introduction outlines the motivation, objectives, and structure of the thesis.
- Chapter 2: State of the Art reviews existing literature on Carnatic music, violin tuning, and computational studies of Indian Art Music, including pitch extraction and intonation analysis methods.
- Chapter 3: Methodology describes the data selection, pre-processing steps, and the computational techniques used for pitch extraction and analysis.
- Chapter 4: Results and Discussion presents the findings of both the swara-wise intonation results and overall section wise comparison metrics.

- Chapter 5: Conclusions and Future Work summarizes the key findings, discusses their implications, and suggests directions for future research.
- Appendix A includes the KDE plots for all the analyzed tracks and sections. Appendix B provides the swara-wise average peak parameters, categorized by rāga and instrument.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Carnatic music

Carnatic music is one of the two main genres of classical music from the Indian subcontinent, primarily associated with the southern part of India, particularly the states of Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Kerala, and Andhra Pradesh, as well as Sri Lanka. The tradition is characterized by its intricate melodic patterns, rhythmic structures, and improvisational elements. It has a rich tradition that dates back several centuries and is deeply rooted in Indian culture and spirituality [4].

As mentioned in the introduction, the fundamental concepts in Carnatic music are *rāga* (the melodic framework) and *tāla* (the rhythmic framework). An octave in Carnatic music consists of seven swaras: Sa, Ri, Ga, Ma, Pa, Da, Ni. With the exception of the tonic (Sa) and the fifth (Pa), each swara has two or three variants as illustrated in Table 1. Additionally, the octave is divided into 21 different intervals, forming the 22-Sruti system which is discussed further in Section 2.3.1.

Semitones from Tonic	swara	Based on C tonic	Interval ratio	In Cents
0	Sa	C	1:1	0
1	Ri1	C#	256:24 or 16:15	90 or 112
2	Ri2	D	10:9	182
2	Ga1	D	9:8	204
3	Ri3	D#	32:27	294
3	Ga2	D#	6:5	316
4	Ga3	E	5:4 or 81:64	386 or 408
5	Ma1	F	4:3 or 27:20	498 or 520
6	Ma2	F#	45:32 or 729:512	590 or 612
7	Pa	G	3:2	702
8	Dha1	G#	128:81 or 8:5	792 or 814
9	Dha2	A	5:3	884
9	Ni1	A	27:16	906
10	Dha3	A#	16:9	996
10	Ni2	A#	9:5	1018
11	Ni3	B	15:8 or 243:128	1088 or 1110

Table 1: Carnatic music swarasthanas, semitone intervals and their corresponding Western notes based on a C tonic, along with the intervals in ratio and cents of the 22-Sruti system

These are known as swarasthanas and total twelve in number, similar to the 12-tone system in western music [5]. Often, the terms swara and swarasthana are used interchangeably, however swara often refers to the actual name of the notes, and each swara can occupy multiple swarasthanas. In the context of a rāga, swaras are arranged into ascending (*aarohana*) and descending (*avarohana*) sequences and serve distinct functions. The arrangement of the swaras in both sequences dictates how the swaras are employed in constructing melodic phrases; swaras in an ascending progression are generally applicable to melodic phrases that ascend, and conversely for descending progressions.

In Carnatic music, a distinctive ornamentation technique involves the employment

of gamakas, which involve either rapid oscillatory movement between swaras (analogous to a pitch modulation), or sliding movements from one swara to another. Depending on the rāga, these are applied to certain swaras, with their usage and intensity varying depending on their features and their relationship with adjacent swaras. However, a swara may be sung steadily in one rāga but with intricate ornaments/gamakas in another, illustrating how two rāgas can differ despite sharing the same swaras. Fundamentally, a rāga's essence is captured in a set of phrases and motifs that embody these characteristics [6]. In Carnatic music, intonation refers to the characteristics of the pitch of swaras, including the position, prominence, and spread, along with their associated ornamentation. [7, 8]. Hence, for a computational understanding and modeling of Indian art music, intonation analysis serves as a fundamental step.

However, unlike other musical tradition where notation serves as a vital resource for both learning and performance, its use is limited in Carnatic music. One of the possible reasons can be the difficulty in notating such ornaments such as gamakas. Additionally, the *Guru-Shishya* system is a traditional method of musical education in Carnatic music where knowledge is passed down from a master (guru) to a disciple (shishya) through direct, personal instruction and oral transmission. Carnatic music has historically been transmitted orally, with emphasis placed on listening, imitation, and memorization. This oral tradition has led to a reliance on direct instruction from the guru rather than written notation [9].

In Carnatic music, the lead performer is usually the vocalist, supported melodically by a violin and rhythmically by a *mridangam*. Additionally, the *tambura* serves to provide a constant drone by repetitively playing the tonic and fifth notes throughout the performance.

2.1.1 Carnatic violin: tuning and performance style

The western violin was introduced in India as early as the 17th century and it has now become the primary melodic accompaniment instrument of the voice in the Carnatic music tradition. However, to integrate with the Carnatic music style, the

violin underwent adjustments in tuning and playing techniques. Its strings are tuned to the tonic and the fifth, such as Pa-SA-pa-sa, aligning with the soloist's tonic, and the playing style mirrors the vocalists phrases and passages, performing elaborate ornamentation, sharp shifts and intricate gamakas. Depending on the section of the performance, these are performed in sync, with a slight delay or taking turns with the lead vocalist [10].

2.2 Computational studies of Indian Art Music (IAM)

2.2.1 The CompMusic project

CompMusic is a research project funded by the European Research Council from 2011 to 2017 and coordinated by Xavier Serra from the Music Technology Group of the Universitat Pompeu Fabra in Barcelona (Spain) [11]. Its primary objective was to enhance the automated characterization of music, with a particular emphasis on cultural nuances. The project pursued research in music information processing, employing a domain-specific knowledge approach. Specifically, the project focused on five distinct music traditions from around the globe: Hindustani (North India), Carnatic (South India), Turkish-makam (Turkey), Arab-Andalusian (Maghreb), and Beijing Opera (China).

2.2.2 Datasets

As part of the project, a music corpora with related software tools called Dunya was developed. The Carnatic corpus includes 2,380 audio recordings (235 concerts, 500 hours), covering 259 artists, 965 compositions, 227 rāgas, 15 tālas, and 15 forms. Previous works utilizing the various datasets that form the corpus have focused on various aspects of musical information retrieval with this dataset, mainly divided into two tasks: melodic analysis and rhythmic analysis.

The Carnatic varnam dataset consists of 28 individual vocal recordings accompanied by tāla cycle annotations and notations in a format suitable for machine interpretation. Previously, this dataset has been applied in the analysis of intonation in

Carnatic vocals [3].

The Carnatic Rhythm Dataset is a collection of audio excerpts from the corpus with manually annotated time aligned markers indicating the progression through the taala cycle, and the associated taala related metadata. This dataset has been utilized for tasks such as beat tracking and onset detection [12, 13].

The Indian Music Tonic dataset comprises audio excerpts from the corpus, each with manual annotations specifying the tonic pitch sung by the lead artist. This dataset has been employed in various approaches aimed at tonic identification tasks [14, 15, 16].

2.2.3 Saraga Carnatic

Saraga collections is a subset of Dunya corpora and is the largest annotated open data collections available for computational research on Indian Art Music [17]. It comprises several hours of music with accompanying time-aligned expert annotations and relevant musical (e.g. *rāga*, *tāla*, form) and editorial (e.g. artist, work, concert) metadata. The Saraga collections were conceived and built as a part of the CompMusic project and is currently maintained by the Music Technology Group at UPF Barcelona. Saraga is divided into Saraga Hindustani and Saraga Carnatic, the latter of which will be used in this thesis. Saraga Carnatic contains 249 total recordings, of which 168 recordings feature distinct microphone recordings of: lead vocal, background vocal (where applicable), violin, mridangam, and *ghatam* (if available). However, due to the live nature of these recordings, the multi-track audios in the dataset exhibit significant background leakage (bleeding), hence these multi-tracks are not entirely isolated from the presence of other instruments.

2.3 Intonation and Tuning

A tuning system, in music, refers to the method or system by which the pitches of musical notes are standardized and organized. Various tuning systems have been devised through history, with developments being incorporated based on the instru-

ments and musical styles of the time.

The Pythagorean Tuning System dates back to around the 6th century BCE, and is based on the ratios of small whole numbers[18]. It is based on the ratio of small whole numbers, particularly the perfect fifth (3:2). While it offers pure fifths and fourths, other intervals like thirds are significantly out of tune, leading to the exploration of alternative tuning systems.

Just intonation predates Pythagorean tuning and has been used in various cultures and styles for millennia, but only gained prominence in Western music during the Middle Ages and Renaissance [19]. The system emphasizes harmonically pure intervals using small whole number ratios, especially for thirds and sixths. However, it presents challenges for instruments that cannot easily change tuning to accommodate different keys or modes. Furthermore, various different types of just intonation tuning systems exist.

Equal temperament is the most widely used tuning system in Western music, and gained prominence during the Baroque period. In equal temperament, the octave is divided into twelve equal parts (semitones). Each semitone is the same size, resulting in a fixed frequency ratio of the $(2^{n/12})$ between adjacent notes. It provides a compromise where all intervals are slightly out of tune compared to just intonation but remain consistent across all keys, and is the standard tuning system in Western music today.

2.3.1 Intonation in Carnatic music and the 22-Sruti system

Intonation in Carnatic music continues to be an active area of study and inherently complex due to the intricate nature of the music form.

One widely used tuning system in Carnatic music is that of 22 *Srutis*, which the Madras Music Academy formally adopted through a resolution in 1927 [20]. The 12 swaras in an octave are divided into 22 possible-Sruti positions, the frequency ratios of which are provided in Table 1. Although the acceptance of this system has been debated, it has nonetheless been extensively discussed and supported in scholarly

literature. The system is believed to be based on aural tuning, where shortening a string by $1/32$ of its previous length—a principle known as the Just Noticeable Difference (JND)—results in approximately 22 steps. Although various scholars have proposed different values for these 22 intervals, the commonly accepted values are derived from cycles of fourths, fifths, and thirds [20].

2.3.2 Previous research

Previous research conducted in the field of intonation analysis in Carnatic music has primarily focused on vocal intonation [21], by extracting pitch contours from the vocal track using the YIN algorithm [22] and plotting weighted histograms. The research investigated the intonation of Carnatic and Hindustani music by examining the positions of the swara peaks in relation to the 22-Sruti system. Findings revealed that vocals in Carnatic music tend more towards Just intonation as opposed to Hindustani music which tends towards Equal temperament. Subsequent research utilizing this approach (but using the Melodia pitch tracking algorithm explained in Section 2.4.3) has demonstrated that even rāgas sharing identical swaras can display differences in the peak positions and other attributes within their pitch histograms [3]. This technique was then utilized to obtain a quantitative description of pitch histograms, and further applied for rāga classification by deriving parameters from histogram peaks and using them as features. However, the additional parameters obtained from this process did not improve the classification process as opposed to using just the amplitude and position of the histogram peaks. To address this limitation, additional efforts were made to integrate context-based distributions of swaras, which incorporate local melodic and temporal context of a given pitch value. A key insight from this study was that analyzing pitch histograms of full performances alone did not provide sufficient insights into intonation. Instead, a more detailed analysis of individual phrases is essential, as intonation can vary significantly depending on the specific phrases and passages.

Previous studies on Carnatic violin intonation, as documented in [23], have yielded inconclusive findings in relation to intonation. The research involved extracting pitch

tracks using three distinct methods: Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), time-domain autocorrelation, and harmonic source separation. Despite these efforts, the study did not provide definitive conclusions regarding intonation. It was observed that different musicians exhibited variations in intonation even when playing the same notes.

Other research undertaken on intonation in Carnatic vocals, mandolin, and violin [24] demonstrated that the Carnatic Violin aligns more closely with Equal Temperament tuning than Just Intonation. However, this study relied on manually recording stable individual notes in the aarohana and avarohana, and estimating the fundamental frequency (f_0). As such, it is not representative of intonation during live performances, as these may exhibit some variation.

In general, it has been observed that simply investigating the frequency intervals of performed notes in Carnatic music does not yield conclusive results on intonation. As notes are typically performed with heavy pitch modulation, it is necessary to investigate the shapes and distributions of peaks of pitch distributions.

Additionally, significant research has not been undertaken computationally in the field of Carnatic violin intonation, despite it being the primary melodic accompaniment in the style. Understanding violin intonation is crucial, as its performance style differs significantly from that of the voice. Previous research has also been limited by the availability of suitable datasets in order to conduct a larger analysis.

2.4 Pitch tracking models

2.4.1 CREPE

CREPE (Convolutional Representation for Pitch Estimation) is a pitch tracking model based on a deep convolutional neural network (CNN), which operates directly on the time-domain waveform input [25]. In general, it shows better performance metrics when compared to traditional pitch tracking algorithms such as pYIN [26] and SWIPE [27].

Its effectiveness can be further enhanced when tailored to specific instruments, as demonstrated by the modification of CREPE trained specifically on *Violin Etudes*, a 27.8-hour violin performance dataset [28].

2.4.2 FTA-Net

Frequency-Time Attention Network (FTA-Net) is a state-of-the-art deep learning based vocal pitch extraction algorithm, where the FTA module mimics human hearing by detecting the predominant melody, and a Selective Fusion module dynamically selects and fuses attention maps created by the FTA-module [29].

Building upon the original FTA-Net, the FTA-Net Carnatic model is specifically tailored to address vocal pitch extraction in Carnatic music [30]. Utilising FTA-Net’s architecture, the model is retrained using a Carnatic-specific dataset called Saraga-Carnatic-Melody-Synth (SCMS), which contains 1235 minutes of vocal performances and accompanying annotations.

One limitation of the CREPE and FTA-Net models is the absence of a pre-trained model specifically trained on the Carnatic violin. Consequently, these existing models struggle to accurately capture the intricate pitch variations of the Carnatic violin and are prone to making bad estimations and octave errors.

2.4.3 Melodia

Melodia is an algorithm that estimates the fundamental frequency of the predominant melody from polyphonic music signals, primarily utilized to extract the vocal pitch track from a mixed signal [31]. It is a salience-based method that revolves around generating and categorizing pitch contours, which are continuous sequences of f_0 candidates organized using heuristics that rely on auditory streaming cues. These cues include factors like harmonicity, pitch continuity, and exclusive allocation.

Figure 1: Block diagram of Melodia’s four main blocks: sinusoid extraction, salience function computation, pitch contour creation and melody selection [31].

It has commonly been used for computational melodic analysis of Carnatic vocals [3, 32, 33, 6].

For the purposes of this research, Melodia has been chosen for violin pitch tracking. As a heuristics-based model, it effectively identifies the predominant melody within the violin multi-track, largely ignoring any leakage from the vocal melody. Additionally, it includes a post-processing step to detect and correct octave errors and pitch outliers.

To ensure consistency in intonation comparison, Melodia has also been chosen for vocal pitch extraction, using the same algorithm parameters.

2.5 Rāga characteristics

2.5.1 Hanumatodi

Hanumatodi (also known as Thodi) is a widely recognized rāga in Carnatic music, and is the 8th melakarta rāga in the 72 melakarta rāga system. It is a sampoorṇa rāga constituting all seven swaras, specifically *Suddha Rishabham (R1)*, *Sadharana Gandharam (G2)*, *Suddha Madhyamam (M1)*, *Panchamam*, *Suddha Dhavatham*

(D1), and *Kaisiki Nishadham* (N2). The equivalent mode in Western music is Phrygian.

A distinctive feature in the performance of Thodi is the use of extensive gamakas, and often times the constituent swaras are not held fixed at their expected swarasthanas. Previous studies have indicated that in a sample of an alaapana 72% of the duration consisted of gamakas, and 28% steady notes [34]. The Hindustani equivalent to Thodi in terms of the swaras is *Bhairavi*, and although they contain the same notes, they differ in their performance styles, with *Bhairavi* characterized by a greater emphasis on notes held at their expected positions.

2.5.2 Kalyani

Kalyani is one of the most celebrated and versatile rāgas in Carnatic music, known particularly as it is performed in auspicious occasions. It is the 65th melakarta rāga, and comprises the swaras *Chatusruthi Rishabham* (R2), *Anthara Gandharam* (G3), *Prati Madhyamam* (M2), *Panchamam*, *Chatusruthi Dhaivatham* (D2), and *Kaakali Nishadham* (N3). The equivalent mode in Western music is Lydian.

Kalyani is characterized by a strong emphasis on gamakas, yet its notes tend to adhere more closely to their swarasthanas compared to Thodi, which typically features more pronounced modulations [35].

Chapter 3

Methodology

Figure 2: Flowchart of Methodology

3.1 Selection of tracks

Four tracks of rāga Thodi and 3 tracks of rāga Kalyani have been chosen for analysis. Saraga contains around 120 min and 82 min of violin performances of Thodi and Kalyani respectively. Of these, 3 track of Thodi and 2 track of Kalyani are full tracks

i.e. they constitute the alaapana, violin solo and main section of the performance. One track from each rāga is a short piece.

3.2 Tonic estimation

An important element of intonation analysis is tonic identification. Pitch histograms are visualised as interval histograms in cents with reference to a tonic frequency of the performance. While Saraga does have annotated tonic frequencies for all the recordings, these are associated with the tonic of the vocalist.

To obtain the tonic of the violin, we apply the Indian art music tonic identification algorithm from Essentia to the multi-track, which is based on the multipitch analysis approach [14].

3.3 Predominant pitch extraction

As described in Section 2.4.3, Melodia has commonly been used for computational melodic analysis of Carnatic vocals. It is a heuristics-based model that generates multiple pitch contours from a polyphonic signal and utilizes auditory streaming cues to identify the predominant pitch contour. This leads to the extraction of better voicing segments and minimises octave errors. Additionally this method is able to distinguish the predominant instrument in a track (in our case the violin), and disregard bleeding from the vocal performer.

The selected violin multi-track is loaded at 16 kHz sampling rate and normalized. A high pass filter (Chebyshev Type II) with cutoff (Tonic - 1) Hz is then applied to the signal in order to reduce interference from any percussion in the pitch estimation process.

An equal loudness filter is then applied to the audio before the pitch estimation process in line with the recommendation from the original paper. The pitch is then estimated using the Melodia algorithm, with the following parameters:

- Frame size: 2048 samples (default)

- Hop size: 120 samples (7.5 ms at 16 kHz)
- Number of iterations for octave errors: 5
- Bin resolution: 1 cent
- Minimum frequency: Tonic (in Hz) - 1

3.4 Pitch processing

Once the raw pitch contour is obtained, it needs to be processed to eliminate incorrect estimations, the details of which are presented in the following sections.

3.4.1 Disregarding low confidence estimations

An essential step in refining pitch contours is to disregard sections where pitch estimation confidence falls below a certain threshold. To achieve this the obtained pitch contour is first separated into voiced segments, and then the median pitch confidence for each segment is calculated. These median confidences are then plotted on a histogram to identify trends, from which a suitable threshold is obtained. Whole voiced segments are then eliminated based on this threshold.

Figure 3: Histogram of mean confidence values for violin segments in *Koluvamaregatha* (Thodi), with the dotted line representing the selected threshold.

A histogram of the discarded pitch estimations is then plotted to verify that the selected threshold does not systematically exclude pitch estimations within a specific frequency range.

3.4.2 Correcting octave errors

Although the Melodia algorithm includes a step for detecting pitch outliers and octave estimation errors, it remains susceptible to octave errors in pitch estimation. To address this, any pitch jumps greater than 700 cents within a 160 ms window are detected and reviewed. If an octave error is identified, it is subsequently corrected using an iterative correction algorithm.

Figure 4: Example of detected octave error in pitch contour, and correction

It's important to note that in intonation analysis, the parameters are derived from histogram peaks that are wrapped to a single octave (See Section 3.5 for more information). In this specific context, octave estimation errors are not necessarily a concern because the data is wrapped into one octave regardless. However, octave correction remains a crucial pre-processing step to ensure accurate pitch contours.

3.4.3 Smoothing the pitch tracks

Figure 5: Example of pitch contour smoothing (above), with algorithm that retains the peaks and dips at the bottom

The raw pitch contour obtained from Melodia is highly quantised and does not accurately represent what the violinist performs. In order to smooth the pitch contour, we use a Savitsky-Golay filter, of suitable window size and order 2, in line with previous works [6]. This is able to smooth the raw contour while preserving its general shape. However the Carnatic violin is capable of playing rapid transitions between notes, which appear as peaks and dips in the contour, and are over-smoothed by the

filter, as shown in Figure 5.

To account for this, for each voicing segment the local maximas and minimas are identified. The filter is then applied separately for each segment, preserving the peaks and dips.

3.5 Pitch histogram computation

Once the processed pitch contour is obtained, the frequency values in Hz are converted to cents based on the tonic frequency estimated in Section 3.2. The cent values are then wrapped to one octave encompassing 0 to 1200 cents.

From this, the pitch histogram is computed with a binsize of 1200, corresponding to a resolution of 1 cent. This histogram is then smoothed through kernel density estimation (KDE) to identify the peaks. Depending on the instrument, the smoothness factor of the KDE is adjusted to achieve a smooth distribution. Typically, vocal histograms require a higher smoothness factor than those for the violin. For each peak, the mean position in cents, mean amplitude, standard deviation in cents, and skewness are calculated by fitting the nearest Gaussian curve using non-linear least squares fitting.

For the purposes of this study, the pitch histograms have been computed for each section of the performance separately. These include violin-alaapana, violin-solo, violin-main, vocal-alaapana and vocal-main. Where the performance does not contain an alaapana, solo and main section, the histogram has been computed for the whole track.

3.5.1 Peak parameterization

The parameters of the pitch histogram peaks provide insights into the intonation of various swaras for the selected section of the performance. Specifically:

- Mean peak position (cents): Reflects the intonation or tuning of the swara

- Standard deviation (cents): Indicates the width of the gamaka or how varied that swara performance is
- Peak amplitude (density): Represents the likelihood of swara's occurrence
- Skewness: Shows the direction of ornamentation related to the swara

Figure 6: Example of KDE of pitch histogram. *Kailasapathe* (Kalyani) - Violin Alaapana. Expected Equal Temperament intervals (solid vertical lines) and Just Intonation intervals (dashed vertical lines) are shown. Best fit peaks are indicated using the dotted black lines.

3.6 Vocal pitch histograms

The vocal pitch histograms are generated using the same approach as for the violin, with slight modifications in the parameters. In the Melodia algorithm, the minimum frequency is reset to the default 80 Hz, as the vocalist can sing below the tonic. Additionally, the tonic is not determined as described in Section 3.2; instead, it is loaded from the available tonic annotation in the Saraga dataset.

3.7 Histogram comparison metrics

The following statistical tests were performed to compare the KDEs of different performance sections:

- T-test: This test compares the means of two distributions. A p-value < 0.05 indicates a statistically significant difference in the means, suggesting a meaningful difference in intonation.
- Mann-Whitney U-test: Compares two distributions non-parametrically. A p-value < 0.05 indicates a statistically significant difference which can be interpreted as a meaningful difference in intonation.
- Cross-entropy: Measures the similarity between two normalized distributions. Higher values indicate significant differences, while a value of 0 means the distributions are identical.

These tests were applied to the following sections of the same track:

- Violin Alaapana vs. Violin Main
- Violin Main vs. Violin Solo
- Violin Alaapana vs. Violin Solo
- Violin Alaapana vs. Vocal Alaapana
- Violin Main vs. Vocal Main

The accompanying code is provided in a GitHub repository github.com/root2pk/masters-thesis

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

The results of the analysis are presented in the appendices. Appendix A contains the KDE figures, with peaks and best fit curves illustrated. Appendix B contains the average peak parameters grouped by instrument and rāga.

4.1 General observations

4.1.1 Spread of distributions

In analyzing the KDE distributions of violin and vocal performances, it is observed that the violin distributions exhibit more distinct and concentrated peaks around each swara, while the vocal distributions are characterized by broader, more diffuse, and noisier peaks. This distinction is quantitatively supported by a comparison of the standard deviation of each peak. The violin distributions consistently show lower standard deviations, indicating narrower peaks. Additionally, the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) further confirms that the violin distributions have a higher signal clarity, with peaks standing out more prominently from the surrounding noise compared to the vocal distributions.

Figure 7: Plot of Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio for violin and vocal alaapana and main sections for all the tracks. Violin sections show higher PSNR compared to their corresponding vocal sections

4.1.2 Violin playing style

A notable feature of Carnatic violin performance is that the tonic (Sa) and fifth (Pa) are typically sustained while the vocalist sings. This is common in both the alaapana and main sections of the performance, where the violin holds these notes—also the open strings in the tuning—between its phrases. This is further supported by the KDEs of the violin sections, which display distinct peaks around 0 and 700 cents, representing a significant proportion of the played notes (combined average amplitude of 0.45 - 0.5, representing 45 - 50% of the played notes).

4.2 Equal temperament vs. Just intonation positions

Owing to the performance style in Carnatic music as detailed in Sections 2.1 and 2.5.1, held notes are typically rare, except in the case of the tonic and fifth as

discussed in the previous section. As a result, attributing intonation solely to the mean peak positions of swara peaks can be challenging, making it difficult to directly relate them to equal temperament or just intonation.

Additionally, there is significant variability in intonation and playing style among performers, likely influenced by the Guru-Shishya tradition mentioned in Section 2.1. Previous studies [21, 24, 3] have also recognised these issues, typically addressing them by focusing on the tuning of sustained notes.

When observing the mean peak positions in cents of the pitch distributions (see Appendix A), there is considerable variability in whether the peaks align more closely with just intonation or equal temperament. Furthermore, the equal temperament system offers only one potential position for each swara, while the 22-Sruti just intonation system provides two potential positions for each swara, except for Pa. As a result, the 22-Sruti system has a higher likelihood of alignment.

4.3 Swara wise intonation

4.3.1 Thodi

In Thodi, the distributions indicated that Suddha Rishabham (R1) often extended into the range of Chatusruthi Rishabham (R2), reflecting significant modulation. Sadharana Gandharam (G2) showed no distinct peaks, highlighting its transient role, while Suddha Madhyamam (M1) was generally sustained with clear peaks. Suddha Dhaivatham (D1) displayed differing intonations between vocals and violin, with vocals sometimes drifting towards D2. Kaisiki Nishadham (N2) exhibited sharper peaks for the violin, contrasting with broader vocal peaks.

Suddha Rishabham (R1)

The pitch histograms generally displayed prominent peaks around 100 cents, suggesting the presence of R1. However, a notable observation was that nearly half of the distributions also showed a peak around 200 cents (R2), which is not theoretically part of the rāga. This aligns with established musicological information that,

in Thodi, the oscillation of Ri can extend well beyond 100 cents, often reaching 150 or 204 cents [34], effectively approaching the swarasthana of R2 [36]. This is further confirmed by an average skewness of -2.3 in the violin distributions.

Sadharana Gandharam (G2)

Although G2 is theoretically a fundamental swara in Thodi, it is never sustained and is typically performed with heavy ornamentation between R1 and M1 [36]. Consequently, none of the histograms exhibited a peak at 300 cents.

Figure 8: Example of how G2 is rendered in Thodi

Suddha Madhyamam (M1)

In general, M1 featured more distinct peaks around the expected mean peak position of 500 cents, with an average amplitude of 0.16 and minimal spread (standard deviation of 14 cents as compared to 50 cents of R1). This pattern was evident in both vocal and violin distributions, confirming that M1 is usually sustained or performed with minimal gamakas [34].

Suddha Dhaivatham (D1)

Most of the violin distributions displayed clear, albeit small, peaks near 800 cents, indicating the presence of D1. In contrast, the vocal distributions were more spread out in this region, with occasional peaks at 900 cents (D2). This indicates a disparity

in the performance style of D1 in Thodi between the vocals and violin. It is known that D1 in Thodi is performed with significant oscillations, often drifting towards and sometimes above D2 [34], which was more prominently observed in the short track *Munnu Ravana*. Additionally, multiple descending phrases were observed in this track where the N2 oscillation drifted to the D2 swarasthana.

Figure 9: Descending phrase from Sa to D2 in Thodi

Kaisiki Nishadham (N2)

Roughly half of the violin distributions indicated a peak near 1000 cents for N2, with these peaks generally being sharper (average standard deviation of 20 cents) compared to the corresponding peaks in the vocal sections (average standard deviation of 71 cents). While the peaks were observed, they were generally wider and more disperse, as N2 is also performed with heavy modulations in Thodi, like R1 and G2 [34]. This is further supported by an average skewness of -1.43, indicating that N2 tends to drift towards N3.

4.3.2 Kalyani

Kalyani showed more consistent intonation across vocal and violin performances. Chatusruthi Rishabham (R2) and Anthara Gandharam (G3) closely aligned with theoretical positions, though G3 exhibited some oscillation towards R2. Prati Madhyamam (M2) often merged with Pa, suggesting its transitional role. Chatus-

ruthi Dhavatham (D2) exhibited smaller and more oscillatory peaks, while Kaakali Nishadham (N3) exhibited differences in intonation between violin and vocal.

Chatusruthi Rishabham(R2)

R2 is observed across all the violin distributions as sharp prominent peaks around 200 cents, with an average standard deviation of 14 cents, minimal skewness of -0.04 and average amplitude of 0.1. This aligns with the understanding that R2 can be approached from both Sa and G3 (explaining the minimal skewness) and, while it can be oscillated, it generally maintains its characteristic pitch [35]. For the vocals, R2 typically exhibits a broader peak (average standard deviation of 22 cents), and the mean peak position at 188 cents, indicating that vocalists typically perform R2 closer to just intonation interval of 182 cents.

Anthara Gandharam (G3)

Prominent peaks are observed around 400 cents for both the violin and vocal distributions, although the average peak position of 385 and 374 cents indicate that G3 is performed more in alignment with the just intonation interval of 386 cents. The vocal peaks show a greater spread, with an average standard deviation of 36 cents compared to the violin's 17 cents. The average skewness of 0.5 and 0.7 indicates that G3 tends to oscillate towards R2 in Kalyani.

Figure 10: G3 performance in Kalyani, with the oscillation to R2 and transition to Pa

Prati Madhyamam (M2)

M2 is a crucial swara in Kalyani, as it provides the characteristic *bhava* of the rāga and contributed to the resolution towards Pa [35]. Interestingly, only one track *Vandalum*, exhibits a peak at 600 cents for both the violin and vocal distributions, with M2 merging into the Pa peak in other distributions. As such, to understand M2's intonation in Kalyani, it is essential to examine the peak of Pa.

Panchamam

Pa exhibits distinct peaks in both the violin and vocal distributions, with average positions at 699 and 687 cents respectively. While the peaks are narrow, the vocal peaks exhibit a higher spread, with an average standard deviation of 30 cents compared to 13 cents for the violin. Particularly in the violin distributions, the Pa peaks occupy a significant proportion, with an average amplitude of 0.3, often encompassing the area around 600 cents (M2) into the Pa peak. This suggests that M2 is generally performed as a passing note to Pa, often leading to an M2-to-Pa resolution in performances.

Chatusruthi Dhaivatham (D2)

D2 peaks appear around 900 cents for both violin and vocal distributions, though they are generally smaller (amplitudes of 0.04 and 0.06, respectively) and relatively wide (standard deviations of 24 cents and 31 cents, respectively). The skew characteristics vary considerably across sections, and no firm conclusions can be made about the direction of the gamakas. D2 is typically performed with oscillations and is rarely sustained, particularly in descending passages [35].

Kaakali Nishadham (N3)

Distinct peaks are consistently observed around 1100 cents for all the violin sections, with an average mean position of 1102 cents, average amplitude of 0.1, and average standard deviation of 20 cents. In contrast, only 2 out of 5 vocal distributions exhibit a peak around N3, with an average mean position of 1098 cents, average

amplitude of 0.14, and average standard deviation of 20 cents. This indicates a disparity in the performance style of N3 between the violin and vocals, with the violin exhibiting clear positions near the theoretical swarasthana, and the vocals tending to perform N3 with heavy oscillation and generally utilizing it as an ornamental swara to approach Sa in the next octave [35].

Figure 11: Pa to Sa and Ga to Pa phrase in *Vandalum*. Notice the gamaka performance in N3 and G3, and the use of M2 as a transitional note to Pa.

4.4 Statistical tests

4.4.1 Variance

When performing the t-tests, it was observed that the variance among violin sections of the same track were equal, allowing for a standard T-test to be used. However, when comparing violin to vocal sections, unequal variance was detected, leading to the use of a Welch's T-test. This suggests that the variance among the KDEs of the violin sections was similar, while there was a greater difference in variance between the vocal and violin KDEs within the same sections.

4.4.2 Comparison metrics

A plot of the T-test stat values, T-test p-values, Mann-Whitney U-test stat values and cross-entropy values are presented in Figure 12. Mann-Whitney test p-values

have not been presented since the p-values for almost all the tests are < 0.05 .

Figure 12: Comparison metrics between sections

T-test stat values

The T-test statistic values for the Kalyani tracks (*Vandalum*, *Sundari Nee Divya*, and *Kailasapathe*) were generally less negative, and in some cases, slightly positive, particularly in comparisons between the violin sections. This suggests that within Kalyani, the pitch distributions across different sections are more similar, indicating consistency in swara rendering.

In contrast, the Thodi tracks exhibit more negative T-test statistic values, especially for violin vs. vocal comparisons. This points to more pronounced differences between violin and vocal performances in Thodi, highlighting variability in swara intonation.

T-test p-values

The Kalyani tracks generally exhibit higher p-values, particularly for the violin alaa-pana vs solo tests and violin vs vocal alaa-pana tests, indicating that the differences between these sections are not statistically significant. On the other hand, Thodi tracks exhibit lower p-values for these tests, highlighting more significant differences between the violin and vocal intonations in Thodi as opposed to a uniform approach in Kalyani.

Cross-entropy values

The cross-entropy values are consistently high across all comparisons, averaging around 6, suggesting that the pitch distributions being compared are notably different in all cases.

Mann-Whitney U-test stat values

The U-test statistic values are consistently high across all tests, with Kalyani tracks showing more consistent results compared to the more varied outcomes in Thodi tracks.

Mann-Whitney U-test p-values

The U-test p-values are not included in the plot since most tests showed extremely low values. The only exceptions were the violin alaa-pana vs. main sections in the tracks 'Kailasapathe' (0.16) and 'Karuna Nidhi Illalo' (0.83), indicating that the differences in violin intonation between these sections are not statistically significant for these tracks.

4.4.3 Summarised metrics

The statistical analysis of Kalyani and Thodi tracks reveals distinct differences in the consistency and variability of swara intonation between the two rāgas. Kalyani tracks exhibit more consistent and uniform intonation across different sections, as

evidenced by higher p-values, lower cross-entropy values, and more similar Mann-Whitney U-test stat values. This suggests that Kalyani is performed with a more standardized approach to pitch across both vocal and violin performances.

In contrast, the Thodi tracks show greater variability in pitch distributions between sections, particularly between violin and vocal performances. The more negative T-test stat values, lower p-values, and higher cross-entropy values for Thodi suggest that this rāga allows for a broader range of pitch modulation and ornamentation, leading to more distinctive differences between performances on different instruments. This could be attributed to the rāga's characteristic gamakas, which allow for wider oscillations and more expressive intonation, especially in the rendering of swaras like Suddha Rishabham (R1), Sadharana Gandharam (G2) and Kaisiki Nishadham (N2).

Additionally, when comparing the metrics for each section, we observe that there is more consistency in the intonation characteristics for the violin alaapana vs. violin main sections, implying that the approach to swara performance in the free-form alaapana is generally maintained even the main section for violin performances. The tests of the violin alaapana vs. solo and violin main vs. solo sections reveal that the violin main and alaapana intonations more closely relate to each other, and the intonation in the solo section shows greater divergence than the other two. The solo is the only section where the violin plays without vocal accompaniment, suggesting that this part may employ distinct expressive techniques or ornamentation, resulting in a more varied pitch distribution.

As expected, across all tracks, the tests between the violin and vocal performances exhibit the most pronounced differences in pitch distribution. This is expected, as pitch distributions between two different instruments for the same section would naturally vary more than those of the same instrument across various sections.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Future work

5.1 Conclusions

This paper has investigated the intonation characteristics of Carnatic violin performances in the rāgas Thodi and Kalyani, with specific focus on analyzing swara-based intonation trends against known musicological insights; and statistically comparing overall intonation between violin sections, and between violin and vocal performances of the same sections. Through a detailed examination of pitch distributions, pitch histograms, and comparison metrics, several key findings have emerged:

5.1.1 Tuning system

Analysis of the mean peak positions in the violin distributions reveal that there is considerable variability in their alignment with either the 22-Sruti just intonation system or equal temperament. Intonation relies heavily on the performer, making it challenging to assign fixed frequency values to a style characterized by extensive ornamentation and microtonality.

5.1.2 Swara wise results

The intonation characteristics of individual swaras have been examined, and while most swaras align with expected musicological information, some discrepancies were

observed between the violin and vocal performances. Specifically it has been observed that there is disparity in the performance style between violin and vocals of Suddha Dhaivatham (D1) in Thodi and Kaakali Nishadham (N3) in Kalyani.

Additionally, it was generally found that vocal distributions exhibit broader, more diffuse, and noisier peaks compared to the sharper peaks observed in violin distributions.

5.1.3 Statistical results

Statistical tests reveal that the intonation of the violin and vocal performances exhibits significant differences across the two rāgas, with Kalyani showing more uniformity in pitch distributions between violin and vocal sections, and Thodi displaying more variability. This suggests that Kalyani is performed with a more standardized intonation approach, whereas Thodi allows for more expressive modulation and variation.

Furthermore for all tracks, intonation appears relatively consistent between the violin main and alaapana sections, but diverges more in the solo section. This suggests that the presence of vocal accompaniment in the alaapana and main sections influences the violin's intonation, whereas the solo sections allow for a more independent and varied intonation style.

5.2 Future work

There are several methods to enhance and extend the research presented in this thesis, focusing on both technical and musicological improvements.

5.2.1 Technical Improvements

One significant technical improvement would be the development of a more efficient and accurate pitch tracking algorithm tailored specifically for the Carnatic violin, potentially using a deep learning based method like the FTA-Net architecture as in

the case of FTA-Net Carnatic. However, this would require a comprehensive dataset of violin pitch annotations, which is a current limitation.

Another technical aspect that is currently still an active topic of research is the refinement of pitch contour smoothing and interpolation techniques. Although these processes may not drastically impact pitch histogram computation, they are crucial for enhancing the overall accuracy of computational analysis in Carnatic music. Improved smoothing and integrating interpolation into the current analysis can lead to more precise pitch contours, which can be useful for more detailed intonation analysis.

5.2.2 Musicological Improvements

As discussed in Section 2.3.2, merely investigating pitch histograms for a whole section of a performance does not necessarily yield meaningful results, as intonation of swaras can vary significantly based on the context of the phrases and passages. A more robust approach to intonation analysis would be to investigate these trends for certain repeated phrases, characteristics passages or aarohana/avarohana sections. This approach would offer a more detailed understanding of how intonation is employed in different rāgas.

In this thesis, comparison metrics were calculated by considering the entire KDE for each section of a performance. While this method provides a general overview of intonation differences, a more granular approach would involve conducting a peak-by-peak analysis. By isolating the peaks corresponding to each swara, particularly those representing key tonal centers in Carnatic music, it would be possible to gain deeper insights into how these swaras are intonated differently across sections or between different instruments.

Further work would include extending the analysis to more rāgas (subject to the availability of clean violin multi tracks), and potentially encapsulating the results to capture a more holistic view of swara intonation of the violin in Carnatic music.

5.2.3 Future Applications

Developing methods to automatically extract accurate pitch contours, identify relevant motifs, and generate histograms for these motifs could have significant implications for future research and practical applications. For instance, such techniques could be leveraged for rāga classification tasks, where the extracted motifs and their corresponding pitch distributions serve as key features for classification models. This would not only advance computational musicology in Carnatic music but could also provide practical tools for music education and performance analysis.

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Appendix A

Kernel Density Estimation figures

A.1 Thodi tracks

A.2 Kalyani tracks

Appendix B

Average peak parameters

swara	Mean (cents)	Standard Deviation (cents)	Skewness	Amplitude (normalized)
s	4	3.69	-1.47	0.12
R1	93	50.26	-2.31	0.18
R2	194	27.83	4.03	0.02
M1	494	14.36	-0.99	0.16
P	699	10.87	0.6	0.19
D1	791	19.34	-1.5	0.04
D2	891	25.28	3.65	0.1
N2	992	20.38	-1.43	0.02
S	1194	6.74	1.06	0.33

Table 2: Average peak parameters (Thodi, violin sections)

swara	Mean (cents)	Standard Deviation (cents)	Skewness	Amplitude (normalized)
s	8	5.08	0.98	0.16
R1	87	68.88	0.59	0.15
R2	185	129.76	0.42	0.5
M1	485	26.43	0.23	0.08
P	699	19.58	1.07	0.21
D1	798	24.48	-0.88	0.02
D2	893	37.89	1.08	0.05
N2	1000	71.95	0.01	0.12
S	1188	8.15	-0.52	0.24

Table 3: Average peak parameters (Thodi, vocal sections)

swara	Mean (cents)	Standard Deviation (cents)	Skewness	Amplitude (normalized)
s	4	4.12	-1.22	0.12
R2	198	14.38	-0.04	0.1
G3	385	17.21	0.52	0.15
M2	599	14.14	3.78	0.03
P	699	13.11	-1.74	0.3
D2	905	24	-0.71	0.04
N3	1102	20.73	1.7	0.11
S	1193	6.28	-1.03	0.18

Table 4: Average peak parameters (Kalyani, violin sections)

swara	Mean (cents)	Standard Deviation (cents)	Skewness	Amplitude (normalized)
s	12	6.56	0.32	0.18
R2	188	22.05	-0.12	0.1
G3	374	36.33	0.74	0.28
M2	607	19.45	1.48	0.04
P	687	29.93	-3.3	0.25
D2	888	30.68	2.74	0.06
N3	1098	19.85	1.96	0.14
S	1183	26.92	-4.33	0.29

Table 5: Average peak parameters (Kalyani, vocal sections)